

**A QUANTITATIVE STUDY ON THE EFFECTS OF TRANSFORMATIONAL
LEADERSHIP ON WORK PERFORMANCE AND
AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT**

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A Quantitative Study on the Effects of Transformational Leadership on Work Performance and Affective Commitment

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Abstract

Transformational leadership is characterized by leaders who inspire and motivate their followers to achieve higher levels of performance and commitment. The study utilized a sample of 185 teachers and 19 administrators from various schools within Mawab District and collected data through surveys measuring transformational leadership behaviors, work performance measures, and affective commitment levels. Results from the study revealed a negative relationship between transformational leadership and both work performance and affective commitment. Specifically, employees who perceived their leaders to exhibit transformational leadership behaviors reported lower levels of work performance and affective commitment. This unexpected finding suggests that the traditional positive association between transformational leadership and employee outcomes may not hold true in all organizational contexts or for all employees.

Keywords: *transformational leadership, task performance, affective commitment quantitative*

Introduction

Leadership has piqued the interest of academics worldwide, with a few scholars discussing it as /a major issue (Bryman, et-al., 2012). One of the primary reasons is that leadership is the most essential driving force in improving organizational performance (Karamat, 2013). In particular, in educational institutions, the function of leader is viewed as essential. It has the potential to play critical roles in improving educator quality and developing relationships both inside and outside of educational institutions (Day Sammons, 2016). However, if these roles are not played well, it will influence organizational commitment and performance.

Transformational leadership is a type of leadership where the leader sets aside his or her self-interest and inspires the followers to adopt his or her values and goals. Transformational leaders inspire their followers through a clear mission, optimism, enthusiasm, and emotional appeals (Phillips & Gully, 2012). They set behaviors to better the workplace and their people. They concentrate on the process of change, particularly when the best leadership is achieved under the environments of fast technological, social, and cultural change (Gulati et al., 2013).

The dynamics of global education migration have been gradually evolving, with an increasing number of educators seek teaching opportunities beyond their native shores.(Smith. 2018). Motivations that drive teachers, particularly those from the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines, to pursue opportunities abroad are multifaceted and deeply rooted in both personal and systemic issues. Studies show that economic Prospects remain one of the most important reasons for this migration, with Smith and Johnson (2016) emphasizes the appeal of higher compensation packages in foreign countries. These potential earnings are often significantly higher than what they may receive. Domestically, offer financial stability and a chance for these educators to provide better They have families. However, it isn't just about economics.

Specifically in the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) has seen a significant number of teachers are opting for overseas placements (Ramirez, 2020). Such Movements have primarily been attributed to a variety of motivations ranging from

Financial stability contributes to professional development and personal goals (Jones & Kim,2017). However, the decision to relocate abroad is not without challenges. Previous research has highlighted the emotional, logistical, and professional challenges teachers face when adapting to new educational settings (Nguyen, 2019).

Furthermore, Smith et al. (2017) discussed the immediate motivations for teachers leaving. They did not track the experiences of these educators over time, even in their home countries. A longitudinal perspective would provide insights into how motivations evolve and challenges. Shift following migration.

In the Division of Nueva Ecija , Central Luzon Philippines, the study conducted by Mangulabnan et al., (2013) on the transformational leadership styles of school principals in Central Luzon revealed that majority of the respondents agreed that the transformational leadership affects the work performance and affective commitment of the teachers and it helps them achieve their goals.

In Pakistani, A study conducted by Khan et al. (2020) showed the significant positive relationship between transformational leadership and working burnout through intrinsic motivation. When a transformational leader indicates support for honest and fair matters associated with employees, the employee feels less exhausted and motivated. Intrinsically motivated employees who are driven by enjoyment and interest in their work are more likely to work hard at their jobs and feel less fatigue, less emotional exhaustion, and increased desire to participate in the organization which would led to poor performance.

In the context of Mawab district, where the researcher is currently teaching, it has been observed leadership is seen to have influenced

the commitment and performance of the teachers. There are some who become passive and are not performing well when the principal is not inspiring and motivating. A number of teachers are also leaving the academe and prefer to work abroad because of school leaders who are not helping the teachers to grow in their field and thus, they experience burn-out. One of colleague in our school don't get along with.

The researcher is inspired to determine the relationship of transformational leadership with work performance and affective commitment of the teachers in the district she belong. The researcher believes that it is essential to if the leadership of the principal those affect the work performance and affective commitment of the teachers.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effect of transformational leadership on the affective commitment and work performance of the teachers in selected schools in Mawab, Davao de Oro. It specifically sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of transformational leadership traits of the principal in terms of:
 - 1.1. idealized influence; and
 - 1.2. inspirational motivation?
2. What is the level of work performance of teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. task performance;
 - 2.2. contextual performance; and
 - 2.3. counter-productive performance?
3. What is the level of affective commitment of teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1. emotional attachment;
 - 3.2. involvement in the organization; and
 - 3.3. identification with the organization?
4. Is there a significant relationship between transformational leadership and work performance?
5. Is there a significant relationship between transformational leadership and affective commitment?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the correlational research strategy and descriptive quantitative research. According to Arikunto (2007), descriptive research is used to collect data from the study, and the correlation method is used to look into the relationship between two variables. Additionally, the correlational statistical test was used to characterize and assess the level of relationship between two or more variables or sets of scores in the correlational research design (Creswell, 2012).

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the teachers from all the schools of Mawab District. There were 185 teacher – respondents and together with their 19 school heads to participate in the study chosen using universal sampling.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents by school*

<i>Name of School</i>	<i>Number of Respondents</i>
Mawab Central Elementary School SPED Center	60
Nuevo Iloco Elementary School	30
Andili Elementary School	30
Malinawon Elementary School	6
Guisok Elementary School	3
Nueva Visayas Elementary School	5
Sawangan Elementary School	4
Lonolono Elementary School	4
Concepcion Elementary School	3
Katipunan Elementary School	3
Bawani Elementary School	7
Tabontabon Elementary School	6
Tan -awan Elementary School	3
Tuboran Elementary School	6
Wilson Condes Elementary School	4
San Vicente Elementary School	5
Mahayag Elementary School	6
Total Respondents	185

Instruments

The study used survey questionnaires to gather the necessary data. The instruments of the study were adapted from Koopmans et al. (2014).

The questionnaire contains questions that would help you discover what kind of work performance and affective commitment you have. The Individual Work Performance Questionnaire (IWPQ) measures task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior.

Validation of the Instrument

The constructed research instrument was presented to the researcher's validators and research adviser for comments and suggestions. The improved instrument were reproduced for the administration to the respondents of the predetermined study group during its prescribed schedules.

Procedure

After the validation of the instrument, the researcher secured a letter of endorsement from the Graduate School Office. A letter to the Division Superintendent was submitted for the conduct of the study. After the approval is sought, another letter was submitted to the school principal of the four selected schools. The schedule of the administration of the instrument was set through the principal. Then, the researcher administered the questionnaire to the respondents and retrieved the completed instrument. Responses were tallied, collated, and analyzed using SPSS software.

Data Analysis

To test the hypotheses formulated, the statistical tools were utilized in the study were the following:

Mean. This was used to examine an association existed between the schools' levels and students' academic achievement at the .05 level of statistical significance. According to Ahmed (2015),

The data gathered was compiled, sorted out, organized and tabulated. These were subjected to statistical treatment, to facilitate the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data. The following tests were employed:

Frequencies and percentage. These were used to determine the frequency distribution of data at certain ratings levels.

Weighted Mean. This was used to describe the level of transformational leadership of the principal.

Correlation analysis. This was used to determine the relationship between the study's independent and dependent variables and to determine the difference between the identified moderating variables.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results obtained from the collected data and the subsequent analysis and interpretation based on the problems presented.

Level of Transformational Leadership

Idealized Influence. Table 2 presents the mean of the level of transformational leadership of principal in terms idealized influence.

Table 2. *Idealized Influence*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Make teachers feel good with my school leadership.	4	Agree
Act in ways that the teachers have complete confidence in me.	5	Strongly agree
I don't act in a manner that I am considered as a role model of the teachers.	2.1	Disagree
Motivate the staff by articulating a compelling vision of the school.	4.6	Strongly agree
Guide attitude of teachers by designing a shared vision of the school.	4.9	Strongly agree
Total Mean	4	Agree

As shown in the table, the item, 'Act in ways that the teachers have complete confidence in me.' has the highest mean of 5 with a descriptive rating of strongly agree. Meanwhile, the item that got the lowest mean was 'I don't act in a manner that I am considered as a role model of the teachers' with a mean of 2.1 and a descriptive rating of disagree.

It can be inferred that most of the principals were confident that they have given trust by their teachers. For the item got the lowest mean the principals are very sure for them self that they were considered as role models of their teachers. The indicator idealized influence got a mean of 4 with a descriptive rating of strongly agree.

Inspirational motivation. Table 3 exhibits the mean of level of transformational leadership of principal in terms inspirational motivation.

Table 3. *Inspirational motivation*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Work with the staff and give them fair autonomy in the school.	3.6	Agree
2. Provide teachers with old ways of looking at school activities that help them improve their respective duties.	4.2	Agree
3. Stimulate teachers to think about school-based routine problems and solve them in new possible ways.	4.3	Agree
4. Use intellectual stimulation to challenge teachers' thoughts, imagination, and creativity.	4.2	Agree
5. Provide the teachers with useless professional advice relevant to each individual.	4.3	Agree
Over-all Mean	4	Agree

The above table shows that the items, 'Stimulate teachers to think about school-based routine problems and solve them in new possible ways' and 'Provide the teachers with useless professional advice relevant to each individual' has the highest mean of 4.3 with a descriptive rating of agree. Meanwhile, the item that got the lowest mean was 'Work with the staff and give them fair autonomy in the school.' with a mean of 3.6 and a descriptive rating of agree.

Based on the result the statement, stimulate teachers to think about school-based routine problems and solve them in new possible ways' and 'Provide the teachers with useless professional advice relevant to each individual' got the highest mean it can be inferred that the principal is positive in giving their teachers ways of innovating their way of solving school-based problem. For the lowest mean also, they are not assured that they had given fair autonomy in the school. The indicator inspirational motivation got an over-all mean of 4 with a descriptive rating of agree.

Level of Work Performance

Task Performance. Table 4 presents the mean on the work performance in terms of task performance.

Table 4. *Task Performance*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. I managed to plan my work so that it was done on time.	3.1	Agree
2. My planning is optimal	3.1	Agree
3. I kept in mind the results that I had to achieve in my work	3.4	Agree
4. I was able to separate main issues from side issues at work.	3.2	Agree
5. I don't know how to set the right priorities.	2.9	Agree
6. I was not able to perform my work well with minimal time and effort.	3.1	Agree
7. Collaboration with others was very productive.	3.2	Agree
Over-all Mean	3.1	Agree

The item 'I kept in mind the results that I had to achieve in my work' has the highest mean of 3.4 with a descriptive rating of agree. Meanwhile, the item that got the lowest mean was 'I don't know how to set the right priorities' with a mean of 3.39 and a descriptive rating of agree. Based on the result in terms of task performance teachers always concern about the results they had to achieve in their work but because of a lot of work in the field they don't know how to set their right priorities.

The indicator task performance got a mean of 3.1 with a descriptive rating of agree. The results revealed that teachers in terms of their level of work performance is at their best.

Contextual Performance. Table 5 shows the mean of work performance of teachers in terms of contextual performance.

Table 5. *Contextual Performance*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. On my own initiative, I started new tasks when my old tasks were completed	3.1	Agree
2. I took on challenging tasks when these were available.	3.1	Agree
3. I worked on keeping my job-related knowledge up-to date.	3.2	Agree
4. I came up with creative solutions for new problems.	3.0	Agree
5. I don't take on extra responsibilities	2.9	Agree
6. I actively participated in meetings and/or consultations.	3.1	Agree
7. I did more than was expected of me	3.1	Agree
Over-all Mean	3.1	Agree

The item 'I worked on keeping my job-related knowledge up-to date got the highest mean of 3.2 with a descriptive rating of agree. Meanwhile, the item 'I don't take on extra responsibilities got the lowest mean of 2.9 with a descriptive rating of agree. In

the aspect of contextual performance teachers are eager to worked on keeping their job-related knowledge it can be conclude that they are willing to undertake series of seminars and training to give their best in the field while teachers are willing to took extra responsibilities beyond their fields. Moreover, the contextual performance got an over-all mean of 3.1 with a descriptive rating of agree.

Counterproductive Performance. Table 6 presents the mean result of work performance of teachers in terms of counterproductive performance.

Table 6. Counterproductive Performance

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. I never complained about unimportant matters at work.	3.2	Agree
2. I made work greater than they were at problems.	3.1	Agree
3. I focused on the positive aspects of work situation, instead of on the negative aspects.	3.1	Agree
4. I spoke with colleagues about positive aspects of my work.	3.1	Agree
5. I did more than was expected to me.	3.2	Agree
6. I sometimes did nothing, while I should have been working.	3.3	Agree
7. I managed to get off from work task easily.	3.2	Agree
Over-all Mean	3.2	Agree

Shown in the table that the item “I sometimes did nothing, while I should have been working’ has the highest mean of 3.30 with a descriptive rating of agree. Meanwhile, the following items ‘I made work greater than they were at problems’ ‘I focused on the positive aspects of work situation, ‘I spoke with colleagues about positive aspects of my work’, got the lowest mean of 3.10 with a descriptive rating of agree. The indicator level work performance in terms of counterproductive performance got an over-all mean of 3.2 with a descriptive rating of agree.

Level of affective commitment

Emotional Attachment. Table 7 presents the mean of the affective commitment in terms of emotional attachment.

Table 7. Emotional Attachment

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. My organization’s success are my success	3.1	Agree
2. When someone criticizes my organization, it feels like a personal insult.	3.0	Agree
3. When someone praises my organization, it feels like a praise to me.	3.0	Agree
4. I do feel emotionally attached to this organization.	3.2	Agree
5. I would be very happy to spend rest of my career with this organization.	3.1	Agree
Over-all Mean	3.1	Agree

The item ‘I do feel emotionally attached to this organization.’ got the highest mean of 3.2 with a descriptive rating of agree. Meanwhile, the following items ‘When someone criticizes my organization, it feels like a personal insult’, and ‘when someone praises my organization, it feels like a praise to me’ got the lowest mean of 3.0 with a descriptive rating of agree.

In the aspect of emotional attachment, we can conclude that teachers are emotionally attach to the organization and they build their own comfort and home in their respective stations. The indicator emotional attachment got a mean of 3.1 with a descriptive rating of agree.

Identification with the organization. Table 8 shows the mean of the affective commitment in terms of identification with the organization.

Table 8. Identification with the organization

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me.	3.2	Agree
2. I do not feel like “part of the family” at my organization.	3.0	Agree
3. When my supervisor encourages me, I believe that my organization is encouraging me.	3.2	Agree
4. This organization has a great impact to me.	3.1	Agree
5. If I left this organization, my personal situation would get better.	3.0	Agree
Over-all Mean	3.1	Agree

As shown in the table above, the item, This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me’ and ‘I do not feel like “part of the family” at my organization’, ‘I believe that my organization is encouraging me’ got the highest mean of 3.2 with a descriptive rating of agree. Meanwhile, the following items ‘I do not feel like “part of the family” at my organization.’, and ‘If I left this organization, my personal situation would get better got the lowest mean of 3.0 with a descriptive rating of agree.

In general teachers recognize the organization has a big impact on their lives, they also felt that the organization pushes them to give out their best. Some of the teachers also felt that they were part of it. The indicator identification with the organization got a mean of 3.1 with a descriptive rating of agree.

Involvement in the organization. Table 9 presents the mean of the affective commitment in terms of the involvement in the organization.

Table 9. *Involvement in the organization*

Item	Mean	Interpretation
1. I do not feel a strong sense of belonging to my organization.	3.1	Agree
2. I really feel as if this organization's problems are my own.	2.9	Agree
3. I am proud to say that I'm part of this organization	3.0	Agree
4. I find my values and this company's values are similar	2.8	Agree
5. I am not proud to tell others that I am part of this organization.	2.8	Agree
Over-all Mean	3.0	Agree

As presented in the table, the item, 'I do not feel a strong sense of belonging to my organization' got the highest mean of 3.1 with a descriptive rating of agree. Meanwhile, the following items "I find my values and this company's values are similar", and 'I am not proud to tell others that I am part of this organization' got the lowest mean of 2.8 with a descriptive rating of agree. The indicator involvement in the organization got a mean of 3.0 with a descriptive rating of agree. This section presents the level of transformational leadership traits of a principal in terms of idealized influence and inspirational motivation.

Significant Relation between transformational leadership and work performance

The table below shows the correlation analysis between transformational Leadership and work performance.

Table 10. *Correlation results between transformational leadership and work performance*

Variables	p-value	Correlation Coefficient	Remarks
Work Performance	0.608	0.126	Not significant
Transformational Leadership			

Correlation was conducted to test the relationship between work performance and transformational leadership, p-value is 0.608 which is greater than .05 and means not significant. It can be gleaned from the table that Work performance and transformational leadership has a positive correlation reflecting from its Pearson-r correlation result which has -.608 and a p-value of 0.0126 which is greater than .05, this implies that work performance of the teachers is not affected by the leadership of its principal. This means that the first null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is a no significant relationship between work performance and transformational leadership.

Significant Relationship between transformational leadership and affective commitment

The table below shows the correlation analysis between transformational leadership and affective commitment.

Table 11. *Correlation results between transformational leadership and affective commitment*

Variables	p-value	Correlation Coefficient	Remarks
Affective Commitment	0.180	0.321	Not significant
Transformational Leadership			

Correlation was conducted to test the relationship between affective commitment and transformational leadership has a positive correlation reflecting from its Pearson-r correlation result which has 0.180 and a p-value of 0.321 which is greater than .05, this implies that affective commitment of the teachers is not affected by the leadership of its principal. This means that the first null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is a no significant relationship between affective commitment and transformational leadership.

Level of Work performance

The level of work performance has an overall mean of 3.13 described as agree. in relation to school principals' transformational leadership styles in Mawab District, it usually indicates a positive correlation. This suggests that employees or teachers in this context perceive their principals to be demonstrating transformational leadership behaviors that are supportive, motivating, and effective in improving overall work performance.

Transformational leadership, which inspires and influences followers to achieve common goals, has been linked to higher job satisfaction, commitment, and motivation among employees. In this case, the "agree" level of work performance may reflect how Mawab District school principals' leadership styles improve teachers' job satisfaction, engagement, and overall effectiveness in carrying out their duties within the educational setting.

A deeper understanding of how these leadership behaviors contribute to the agreed-upon level of work performance among teachers in Mawab District schools would come from further examination of the specific elements of transformational leadership demonstrated by the school principals, such as idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration.

Work performance is the result of an individual putting forth the necessary effort or seriousness to complete a task given to him with his knowledge, expertise, and sincerity in accordance with the duties assigned to him (Garnida, 2017). According to Hasibuan (2014) in Sumendal et al. (2018), work performance is the ultimate result of a person's work in completing duties that have been assigned to him based on his skills, experience, sincerity, and availability. According to Adnyani & Dewi, (2019), job performance is the ability an individual possesses to carry out a variety of tasks connected to their position's needs.

Level of affective commitment

The level of affective commitment as indicated by teachers as agree has an overall mean of 3.07. As a result, the positive correlation between transformational leadership styles and the "agree" level of work performance likely signifies a conducive and motivating work environment fostered by school principals, ultimately leading to improved outcomes and achievements within the educational institution.

When the level of affective commitment is described as "agree" within a workplace context, it indicates a strong emotional attachment and identification that employees have towards their organization. In this scenario, where affective commitment is perceived positively, employees are likely to exhibit loyalty, dedication, and a sense of belonging towards their organization. This emotional connection plays a crucial role in enhancing employee motivation, job satisfaction, and overall performance.

Teachers who exhibit a high degree of affective commitment are more likely to go above and beyond the call of duty, be willing to put in extra effort, and actively participate in the organization's success. They are inspired to uphold the organization's values and mission because they take pride in being a part of it.

Organizations with a workforce characterized by high levels of affective commitment often experience lower turnover rates, higher productivity levels, and increased employee engagement. This emotional bond fosters a positive work environment where employees feel supported, valued, and connected to the organization's goals and objectives.

Moreover, a culture of affective commitment can lead to stronger teamwork, better communication, and improved collaboration among employees. When individuals feel emotionally invested in their organization, they are more likely to work cohesively towards common goals, leading to enhanced performance outcomes and organizational success.

In conclusion, the presence of "agree" level of affective commitment signifies a workforce that is emotionally engaged, dedicated, and loyal to the organization. This emotional attachment not only benefits individual employees in terms of job satisfaction and motivation but also contributes to the overall success and effectiveness of the organization as a whole.

People can work hard, accept the goals and objectives of their employers, and contribute to the success of the organization with the help of affective commitment (Hashmi, Ahmad, & Nawaz, 2021; Ullah, Kamran, Akram, Nawaz, & Rehman, 2021). Affective commitment should lead to greater levels of dedication, happiness, and retention at work (Javeria, 2013; Khan & Iqbal, 2020b). It becomes an ongoing commitment when someone weighs the perceived value of the time, money, and effort invested in the business before leaving. A sense of duty to stay with an organization is the final element, often known as normative commitment. Employees are more inclined to stick with a business if they feel that doing so is both morally and legally correct (Muhammad, Afridi, Ali, Shah, & Alasan, 2021).

Level of Transformational Leadership

The level of transformational leadership as indicated by teachers as agree has an overall mean of 4. Transformational leadership is known for its ability to create a shared vision, empower teachers, and encourage innovation and growth. A mean score of 4 reflects that teachers likely feel motivated, supported, and engaged under this leadership style. They may see the leader as charismatic, able to communicate a clear vision, provide individualized support, and foster a sense of collective purpose and commitment among the teaching staff.

However, it's essential to delve deeper into the specific dimensions of transformational leadership to understand which aspects are contributing most to the favorable mean score. This can involve analyzing factors such as intellectual stimulation, individualized consideration, inspirational motivation, and idealized influence to gain insights into what teachers appreciate and what areas might need further attention for continuous improvement.

Overall, a mean score of 4 suggests a strong endorsement of transformational leadership among teachers and can serve as a positive foundation for fostering a collaborative and high-performing educational environment.

According to Robles (2012), a person's high-tech knowledge is still insufficient in the present, where unique qualities are highly valued. People with particular qualities, such as information exchange efficiency, are increasingly in demand since it is expected that they would perform well in the current competitive labor market (Lazarus, 2013). The head officers are given a solid foundation to work from and can hone their interpersonal skills thanks to their headship identity or description (Mencl, Wefald, & Van Ittersum, 2016).

Transformational leadership is one of the organizational behavior and management concepts that has received the most investigation (Gulati et al., 2013). In addition to influencing employee engagement, commitment, and business unit performance, transformational

leadership also has consequences that are rarely observed in organizations led by other kinds of leaders.

Because of their compelling vision, transformational leaders may persuade their people to put aside self-interest and dedicate themselves to achieving more than is necessary. Strong vision-driven leaders typically have followers who view activities as difficult, intriguing, and significant; as a result, they set performance requirements above average (Yukl, 2006)

Relationship between the work performance and transformational leadership

Based on the statistical calculations summarized in Table 10, it is concluded that transformational leadership have a negative and insignificant effect on the work performance of teachers in Mawab District. Evidenced by the t-statistics value 0.126 is higher than 1.96 and the p-value 0.608 is greater than 0.05. That is, the first hypothesis (H1) was supported or accepted.

Several studies revealed that transformational leadership and intention to quit are negatively related. For instance, Amankwaa and Anku-Tsede (2015) investigated the relationship of transformational leadership and intention to quit on bank employees in Ghana. The results indicated that the presence of transformational leadership diminishes employees' intention to quit, and the availability of alternative job opportunities has no moderating effect on transformational leadership and intention to quit relationship. Sun and Wang (2017) also explored how transformational leadership impacts the intention to quit using structural equation modeling.

Based on the result of study it can be anchored with Sun and Wang (2017) that there is no relationship between the transformational leadership and work performance of the teachers. They never affect each other.

As mentioned earlier, the process of transformation in industry as the main indicator for transformational leadership variables only lasts for a short amount of time. Transformation begins with changes in organizational structure, appointment of new leaders, and then changes in work systems and culture. Respondents of this research felt that the performance of employees in the industry was not affected by the changes above, because the process lasted for a short amount of time. Nevertheless, this research is in line with the conclusions of the research (Fayzhall, Asbari, Purwanto, Basuki, et al., 2020; Fayzhall, Asbari, Purwanto, Goestjahjanti, et al., 2020; Hutagalung et al., 2020; Purwanto, MayestiWijayanti, et al., 2019; Purwanto, Wijayanti, et al., 2019; Purwanto, Asbari, & Hadi, 2020a, 2020b; Purwanto, Asbari, Prameswari, et al., 2020c) which found evidence that leadership had no significant effect on work performance.

The variable of transformative leadership is said to have no effects on work performance and affective commitment in some earlier studies. The case's explanation and confirmation through this study bolster the prevailing idea. Affective commitment and transformational leadership do not significantly affect the teachers' work performance in the Mawab District when the other variables used in this study, such as work performance and affective commitment, are considered as the object. Finally, this study attempts to provide theoretical and empirical contributions to the subject of transformative leadership both within the context of work performance and more broadly.

Relationship between the affective commitment and transformational leadership

Based on the statistical calculations summarized in Table 11, it is concluded that transformational leadership have a negative and insignificant affect on the affective commitment of teachers in Mawab District. Evidenced by the t-statistics value 0.321 and the p-value 0.186 is greater than 0.05. That is, the first hypothesis (H2) was supported or accepted.

Conclusions

Based on the findings that transformational leadership of school principals is not associated with the work performance and affective commitment of teachers, it is important for educational institutions to reevaluate their leadership strategies. While transformational leadership has been widely praised for its ability to inspire and motivate employees, it is clear that it may not be the most effective approach in all situations. One possible explanation for this disconnect could be that teachers may have different expectations and preferences when it comes to leadership style. It is essential for school principals to understand the needs and preferences of their staff in order to effectively lead and support them. This may require a more personalized approach to leadership, where principals adapt their style based on the unique characteristics and needs of each individual teacher.

Additionally, it is crucial for school principals to consider the organizational culture and climate within their school. While transformational leadership may be effective in some settings, it may not align with the existing culture and values of a school. In these cases, principals may need to explore alternative leadership approaches that are better suited to the needs and expectations of their staff. Overall, these findings underscore the importance of ongoing research and evaluation of leadership practices in educational settings. School principals should continuously assess the impact of their leadership style on teacher performance and commitment and be willing to adapt and evolve their approach as needed. By creating a supportive and effective leadership environment, principals can help to ensure the success and well-being of their teaching staff.

Based on the conclusions derived from the results of the study, the following recommendations are hereby presented:

Future studies may be conducted such as principal's organizational management for instructional improvement that can influence schools' performance.

A similar study needs to be carried out in the private schools in the region to establish whether transformational leadership styles have a significant effect on the work performance and affective commitment of private school teachers.

The theories that have been developed in this research can be further developed and continued in the future research conduct, to create more comprehensive model for transformational leadership, work performance and affective commitment.

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